

Position Paper: The Use and Importance of Open Research Information in Research Intelligence

Introduction

Open research information (ORI) can become a crucial aspect of research intelligence in the near future, enabling institutions to understand research activities, assess impact, and guide strategic decision-making. ORI encompasses openly available metadata about publications, datasets, grants, projects, researchers, and institutions. [The SURF Open Research Information \(ORI\) Program 2025–2030](#) in the Netherlands outlines a national vision where all information on publicly funded research is openly available and reusable, reflecting a shift away from dependence on proprietary systems. Professional communities such as the [Research Intelligence Network Netherlands \(RINN\)](#) support this transition by connecting experts and improving shared practices across institutions.

In this document we explain the position of RINN towards ORI, underline its potential importance for sustainable research intelligence practices and why we support the transition.

Context and background

The shift toward OR is embedded within the broader global Open Science (OS) movement, which not only promotes transparency, accountability, and reusability of, but also increasingly serves as a foundational pillar for research policy, funding mandates, and institutional strategy. This strategic alignment underscores the growing recognition that open, high-quality research information plays an important role in a more robust, equitable, and evidence-based research system. In this context, ORI is not

merely a technical development, but a deliberate transformation in how research outputs, actors, and processes are documented, connected, and evaluated.

Within this broader landscape, the ORI movement has begun to develop its own distinct focus and momentum, particularly through initiatives aimed at opening up core scholarly metadata. Key developments include the push for open citations and open abstracts, driven by initiatives such as the Initiative for Open Citations (I4OC) and the Initiative for Open Abstracts (I4OA). Similarly, infrastructures such as OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, Crossref, and DataCite contribute to a federated and interoperable knowledge graph, where persistent identifiers (PIDs) (e.g., DOIs, ORCIDs, RORs) form the backbone of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) research information. These efforts are complemented by policy-oriented frameworks such as the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information, which calls for transparent, community-governed, and open infrastructures as a default for research information systems. Together with emerging best practices and clear, actionable guidelines, these initiatives are shaping ORI into a coherent movement with shared principles and implementation pathways.

ORI is also relevant for broader changes to research evaluation practices. International initiatives like CoARA and DORA and the Rewards and Recognition program in the Netherlands argue for a move toward more holistic and nuanced forms of assessment. As a more community-driven movement, ORI can be more responsive to these changing demands, and could enable the inclusion of a broader range of research outputs and contributions, including datasets, software, protocols, peer review activities, and societal engagement. This expansion creates space for recognizing diverse forms of scholarly work and aligns evaluation practices more closely with the principles of OS. In turn, this can incentivize researchers to adopt open practices not only as a compliance requirement, but as an integral part of scholarly recognition and reward systems.

Professional networks like RINN play a critical role in the adoption and effective use of ORI. RINN serves as a community of experts across research intelligence, library services, and policy advising. It fosters shared best practices and promotes responsible use of research information in assessment and strategic decision-making. Through networking events and community-driven initiatives, RINN helps translate national programs such as ORI into institutional action.

The strategic value of Open Research Information

RINN takes the following position regarding the strategic value of ORI:

Open research information delivers strategic value for research intelligence by enabling transparent evaluation and data-driven decision-making. By replacing closed proprietary systems with open, interoperable infrastructures we reduce vendor lock-in, enhance flexibility and enable context-sensitive evaluation, crucial in the context of the recognition and reward movement and Open Science.

ORI provides transparency in how research is produced, funded, shared, and evaluated, but its significance extends beyond normative ideals of openness and inclusivity. Traditional research intelligence has long relied on proprietary bibliographic databases, which are often characterized by high subscription costs, opaque inclusion criteria, and strict limitations on data reuse. While these systems have delivered relatively high data quality and stability, their proprietary nature constrains how research information can be accessed, interpreted, and repurposed. The ORI program therefore frames the transition to open infrastructures not only as a value-driven choice, but increasingly as a strategic and operational necessity.

Importantly, debates around ORI often emphasize ideals such as transparency, inclusivity, and openness. While these principles remain central, they are not always sufficient to convince more skeptical stakeholders. For broader adoption, ORI must also demonstrate a clear business case. This includes reducing long-term dependency on proprietary vendors, enabling cost control through shared infrastructure, and providing institutions with greater flexibility in how research information is used. ORI can serve as a foundational layer for research intelligence analyses aiming at enhancing research strategy, policy-making, and evaluation, supporting functions such as grant assessment, institutional benchmarking, and recognition and rewards frameworks.

In this regard, the added value of ORI lies in its ability to support more context-sensitive and adaptable approaches to research evaluation. Unlike proprietary systems, where indicators and metrics are often predefined and embedded in closed algorithms, open infrastructures allow institutions to design and adapt indicators in line with their own strategic priorities and disciplinary contexts. This flexibility is particularly relevant in light of ongoing reforms in research assessment, where there is a growing need to move beyond standardized, publication-centric metrics toward more diverse and responsible evaluation practices.

Open infrastructures play a key role in enabling this shift by aggregating interoperable metadata at a global scale. Through the use of PIDs and shared standards, they make it possible to connect information about publications, datasets, software, funding, and researchers across systems.

At the same time, it is important to acknowledge that proprietary systems have also invested heavily in improving their data quality, coverage, and analytical capabilities. This raises a strategic question for institutions: where should limited resources for data improvement be allocated? From an ORI perspective, there is a strong argument that investments in metadata quality and infrastructure are more impactful when directed toward open systems, where improvements benefit the entire research community rather than reinforcing competitive advantages within proprietary ecosystems.

Ultimately, ORI also serves as a means to strengthen digital sovereignty and reduce vendor lock-in. Dependence on proprietary systems not only limits transparency, but also constrains institutional autonomy in shaping research evaluation and policy. By contrast, community-governed infrastructures offer a pathway toward greater collective control over research information, even if this requires sustained investment and coordination.

Building on this, the value of ORI can be understood as cumulative. Transparent, interoperable research information is essential for making research outputs FAIR, but also for enabling robust evaluation, informed decision-making, and equitable recognition of diverse contributions. As highlighted in the SURF ORI program, high-quality and accessible research information underpins activities ranging from grant evaluation to institutional strategy, while also safeguarding core academic principles such as transparency, independence, and accountability. While these arguments retain an element of idealism, they ultimately converge with practical considerations: without open, reliable, and community-governed information infrastructures, the research system risks remaining dependent on opaque and externally controlled data sources that limit both innovation and trust.

Challenges

While the rationale may be convincing, there are still considerable challenges to overcome. The transition to ORI is complex and resource-intensive, and institutions that are not yet ready to fully shift can take a phased approach—continuing to rely on existing systems while gradually investing in open infrastructure, skills, and metadata quality.

Data quality and interoperability

There are great concerns about metadata quality coming from open systems, such as incomplete identifiers, inconsistent affiliations, and uneven coverage. Their key advantage, however, is that these gaps are transparent and can be improved collectively by publishers, institutions, and researchers. Current shortcomings partly reflect historical priorities, where the metadata of non-traditional outputs received less attention, making metadata quality as much a cultural as a technical issue.

While open platforms may still lack robustness for some high-stakes uses and require extra effort for data harmonization, these limitations are best seen as part of a system in transition. With growing adoption of standards, PIDs, and shared infrastructure, improvements depend on coordinated community investment, allowing metadata quality to increase gradually over time.

Cost considerations and sustainability

ORI reduces dependency on proprietary platforms and increases institutional control, but it is not “free” in the sense of requiring no investment. Moving to open infrastructures demands ongoing resources for metadata curation, technical maintenance, and governance, as well as the development of new skills to manage and integrate data. In practice, many institutions will have to operate in a hybrid model, maintaining proprietary systems while gradually building open capabilities.

In addition, sustainability is also a question of how institutions decide which infrastructures to support. Since the ORI landscape would consist of multiple actors and platforms, limited resources need to be allocated strategically and collaboratively. Institutions and research intelligence communities may need shared criteria and deep involvement to assess which infrastructures are worth supporting, considering factors such as long-term funding models, metadata quality, relevance, and user-friendliness for hands-on users. Investment may become fragmented and efficiency of the transition is at risk without a clear vision and collective efforts for ORI.

This transition therefore requires long-term commitment rather than short-term cost savings. While it may initially increase complexity and costs, sustained investment enables greater autonomy, flexibility, and alignment with academic values over time. The strategic value of ORI lies in its potential to deliver more adaptable and community-governed research information systems, provided institutions are willing to invest in capacity, coordination, and continuous improvement.

Other Challenges

ORI continues to face technical challenges, including inconsistent metadata quality, limited interoperability, and risks introduced by scaling efforts such as data expansion and integration. Increasing data volume can amplify issues like duplication, inaccuracy, and semantic noise, highlighting that reliable research intelligence depends as much on data curation and transparency as on data availability.

At a structural level, ORI remains partly dependent on proprietary publishers, since they currently control much of the metadata. Full independence is an unrealistic goal in the short term. In addition, institutional alignment is often limited: commitments to ORI are not always embedded across organizations, requiring broader engagement beyond support staff to include leadership, HR, policy functions, and the researchers themselves

In addition, challenges also persist in research assessment practices, where traditional publication- and citation-based metrics continue to dominate in many disciplines despite reform efforts. This limits incentives for improving metadata and adopting open practices, particularly for non-traditional outputs. Addressing these issues requires coordinated cultural and organizational change alongside technical development.

Future directions

Future directions for ORI focus on strengthening metadata quality, interoperability, and governance through sustained investment in transparent and well-curated data infrastructures. As open systems scale, greater emphasis is needed on improving data integration processes and ensuring that increased coverage does not compromise consistency or reliability.

At the same time, progress depends on broader structural change: reducing dependency on proprietary data sources in a balanced way, aligning institutional strategies beyond support functions, and reforming research evaluation to move beyond publication-centric metrics. Ultimately, advancing ORI requires coordinated efforts in infrastructure, skills, incentives, and cultural change to enable more transparent, context-sensitive, and inclusive research intelligence.

Conclusions

ORI can transform research intelligence by supporting transparency, reducing dependency on proprietary systems, strengthening data quality, and enabling responsible research assessment. National initiatives like the ORI program and professional communities like RINN can be essential drivers of this transition. As global infrastructures continue to expand and integrate, the research community must ensure that openness is accompanied by high-quality metadata, equitable representation, and shared stewardship. The future of research intelligence will depend on how effectively institutions, networks, and infrastructures collaborate to build a truly open, resilient, and inclusive research information ecosystem.

Recommendations to and from the RINN community

The transition to a research landscape where ORI is the norm requires sustained investment, coordination, and collective stewardship. The Awareness–Advocacy–Action framework should therefore be understood as a lens for addressing the challenges of ORI adoption rather than a linear progression. Awareness helps stakeholders understand the opportunities and limitations of ORI; advocacy builds institutional support and shared commitment; and action translates these into investments, capabilities, and practices. These dimensions can occur simultaneously and at different scales, depending on organisational context, resource constraints, and the roles of individual stakeholders.

1. Awareness: Understand the opportunities and trade-offs of ORI

- Recognise ORI as a strategic investment, not just a cost-saving exercise. Open infrastructures reduce dependency on proprietary platforms and increase institutional autonomy, but they require sustained investment in metadata, technical maintenance, governance, and skills of professional staff members.
- Prioritise open and interoperable data sources where feasible. Explore infrastructures such as Crossref, DataCite, OpenAlex, and national ORI initiatives to better understand their strengths, limitations, and potential roles within existing workflows.
- Adopt PIDs. Consistent use of ORCID, DOI, ROR, and grant identifiers strengthens interoperability and reduces future integration challenges.
- Understand the importance of metadata quality. Open infrastructures are only as useful as the quality of the metadata they contain. Identifying gaps and limitations should be part of routine research intelligence practice.

- Develop literacy in responsible use of ORI. Users should understand data provenance, coverage limitations, methodological assumptions, and potential biases when working with any open or closed data sources.
- Recognise representation and equity challenges. No single infrastructure fully represents global research. Analyses should be complemented with regional, national, local and disciplinary sources where appropriate.
- Engage in discussions about the future of research intelligence. Explore how research intelligence can evolve beyond platform dependency toward more transparent, interoperable, and community-governed ecosystems.

2. Advocacy: Build collective commitment and shared direction

- Advocate for a long-term vision for ORI. Emphasise that sustainable adoption requires ongoing commitment rather than short-term projects or isolated technical initiatives.
- Promote hybrid transition strategies. Recognise that many institutions will continue using proprietary systems while gradually developing open capabilities. The goal is not immediate replacement but reducing dependence over time.
- Advocate for open metadata policies and standards. Encourage institutional support for initiatives such as the Barcelona Declaration and other efforts that promote open, reusable research metadata.
- Promote shared criteria for infrastructure investment. Research intelligence communities should collectively discuss how to evaluate and prioritise infrastructures based on sustainability, governance, metadata quality, relevance, usability, and community adoption.
- Engage actively in professional networks and communities. Collaboration through RINN and similar initiatives can reduce duplication of effort, share lessons learned, and coordinate investments.
- Advocate for responsible research assessment using ORI. Encourage evaluation approaches that move beyond narrow publication metrics and better reflect diverse forms of research contribution.
- Encourage publishers and service providers to support open metadata. Open citations, abstracts, affiliations, and identifiers should become standard expectations in negotiations and partnerships.
- Promote ORI as a shared institutional responsibility. Success depends on engagement from leadership, research offices, libraries, IT teams, analysts, and researchers rather than a small group of specialists.

3. Action: Invest in sustainable and coordinated ORI adoption

- Strengthen internal capabilities and reduce strategic dependency. Build expertise in research information management, metadata standards, bibliometrics, data engineering, and open infrastructures.
- Invest in skills development. Support training in APIs, programming, data integration, metadata curation, and data stewardship to enable effective use of ORI.
- Develop sustainable hybrid research intelligence workflows. Combine open infrastructures with existing systems while progressively increasing the role of open data sources.
- Establish processes for metadata quality improvement. Dedicate resources to metadata curation, validation, enrichment, and feedback mechanisms that benefit both local and shared infrastructures.
- Coordinate investments across institutions and communities. Rather than supporting many disconnected initiatives, collaborate on shared priorities and infrastructure needs to maximise impact and sustainability.
- Contribute back to the ORI ecosystem. Support infrastructure providers through participation, governance, feedback, metadata contributions, and where possible, financial investment.
- Embed transparency and reproducibility into research intelligence workflows. Document data sources, methodologies, transformations, and indicators to build trust and accountability.
- Integrate ORI into institutional assessment, reporting, and open science monitoring. Use open metadata to support responsible evaluation and track a broader range of research activities and outputs.
- Develop governance frameworks for infrastructure selection and support. Establish clear principles for deciding which infrastructures to adopt, contribute to, and sustain over the long term.

Looking ahead: A mature ORI ecosystem

A desirable future for ORI is not one where proprietary systems disappear entirely, but one where institutions have meaningful choices and greater control over their research information landscape. Such a future would be characterised by:

- Reduced dependence on any single provider, whether proprietary or open.
- A diverse but coordinated ecosystem of interoperable infrastructures supported by shared standards and governance.

- Collective stewardship, where institutions are contributors rather than merely consumers of research information services.
- Transparent and reproducible research intelligence practices grounded in openly available methods and data.
- Inclusive and representative coverage that better reflects regional, multilingual, and non-traditional research outputs.
- Sustainable investment models that balance local institutional needs with collective community priorities.
- Research assessment approaches that value context, diversity, and quality, rather than relying primarily on narrow quantitative indicators.

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